

Dental topographic analysis of living and fossil lorisooids: investigations into
markers of exudate feeding in lorises and galagos

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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1 **Abstract**

2 Studies integrating patterns of molar morphology and diet are particularly useful for
3 addressing questions of evolutionary history and diet in extinct taxa. However, such studies are
4 lacking among lorisoids when compared to other primates. Lorisioidea is distinctive when
5 considering diet as some taxa consume large quantities of gums or exudates, whereas others
6 consume none. Although there has been previous study of the relationship between craniodental
7 form and exudate feeding, little is known about how patterns of exudate feeding covary with
8 variation in molar topography. We analyzed a sample (n = 52) of lorisoids representing 17 extant
9 taxa and one extinct taxon (*Karanisia clarki*). We used dental topographic metrics to quantify
10 functional aspects (i.e., curvature, complexity, and relief) of occlusal morphology. We also used
11 ancestral state reconstruction to estimate topographic parameters for the last common ancestors
12 (LCA) of Lorisioidea, Lorisidae, and Galagidae. As with previous studies, we found that higher
13 topographic values characterize insectivores, whereas frugivores tend to have lower values. We
14 reconstructed the LCA of Lorisioidea, Lorisidae, and Galagidae as insectivorous, with Lorisidae
15 slightly more insectivorous, and potentially more exudativorous than Galagidae. Moreover, we
16 identified a significant interaction between the primary dietary component (i.e., fruit or insects)
17 and the level of exudate feeding in our sample, with exudate-feeding insectivores being
18 associated with lower topographic values than exclusive insectivores. Finally, we reconstruct *K.*
19 *clarki* as an insectivore, contrary to previous findings, though whether or not the animal fed on
20 exudates remains ambiguous. Overall, our results provide a framework for testing ecological
21 hypotheses about lorisoids and may point to a unique pattern of molar topography among
22 exudativores.

23 **Key Words**

24 Gummivory, Dirichlet normal energy, orientation patch count, relief index, strepsirrhines

25

26

27 **Introduction**

28 The relationship between the morphology of primates' dentition and their diet is well-
29 established in the literature (e.g., Allen et al. 2015; Boyer 2008; Bunn et al. 2011; Bunn and
30 Ungar 2009; Fulwood et al. 2021; Gregory 1922; Kay 1975, 1978; Kay and Covert 1984; Ungar
31 2002, 2004, 2009; Winchester et al. 2014). Most such studies consider how dental morphology
32 varies using a typology of diets that includes some combination of the categories folivore,
33 frugivore, insectivore, omnivore, and hard-object feeder. However, there is another dietary
34 category that is often overlooked when it comes to the study of dental form: exudativory, the
35 consumption of gums and/or saps (Burrows and Nash 2010). Exudativory is rare among
36 mammals, with only members of the genus *Petaurus* (marsupials commonly referred to as sugar
37 gliders), and some primates known to regularly consume exudates (Burrows et al. 2020; Burrows
38 and Nash 2010; Mittermeier et al. 2013; Nash 1986; Smith 2010). Of the roughly 375 species of
39 living primates, at least 69 are known to consume some exudates, either seasonally or
40 opportunistically; however, only a few primate taxa can be characterized as intensive or obligate
41 exudate feeders, where more than 50% of the year-round diet is made up of exudates (Burrows et
42 al. 2020; Burrows and Nash 2010; Smith 2010). With the exception of marmosets, most
43 intensive exudate feeders are strepsirrhines and specifically lorisooids, with some lorises
44 (*Nycticebus* spp.) and bushbabies (*Euoticus*, *Otolemur*) consuming high levels of exudates year-
45 round (Burrows et al. 2015, 2020; Burrows and Nash 2010).

46 Previous scholars (Burrows et al., 2010, 2015, 2020) have examined dental signals for
47 exudate feeding among primates and note a few key features associated with this feeding
48 behavior, and particularly among those taxa that gouge or scrape to extract gums. For example,

49 exudate feeding taxa tend to be characterized by a reduction in the relative size of the lower third
50 molar compared to closely related, non-exudate feeding taxa. Intensive exudate feeding
51 bushbabies are characterized by relatively larger premolars and upper canines and more robust
52 toothcombs, and the exudate feeding slow loris *Nycticebus* is characterized by a more robust
53 toothcomb relative to non-exudate feeding lorises (Burrows et al.2015). Gum-feeding marmosets
54 that gouge (e.g., *Cebuella*) are characterized by thinner lingual enamel relative to the labial
55 enamel on the incisors relative to non-gouging tamarins (e.g., *Saguinus*) (Rosenberger 1978).
56 Other gouging taxa, such as *Nycticebus*, also show this pattern of differential enamel thickness
57 on the lingual vs. labial aspect of the anterior dentition (Selig et al., 2019a). As such, it is a
58 feature thought to strengthen the anterior teeth and reduce stress when the animal gouges its teeth
59 into trees to extract gums (Selig et al., 2019a). However, there has been less examination of the
60 association between the occlusal morphology of the molars and gum feeding.

61 Previous work examined the dental morphology of several platyrrhine primates using
62 dental topographic analysis (DTA) and included specimens of *Callithrix*, which are known to
63 consume high levels of gums (Ungar et al., 2018). This study showed that *Callithrix* has high
64 topographic values (i.e., high angularity) and it argued that gums likely have little selective
65 pressure on the topography of the molars and suggested that the secondary diet of *Callithrix*,
66 insects, requires sharp, pointed teeth to pierce chitinous exoskeletons (Ungar et al., 2018).
67 Subsequent work classified platyrrhine exudativores with a reasonably high level of accuracy
68 based on a combination of characteristic DTA values (“medium-low OPCR and medium-high
69 RFI, in combination with small size, as measured by 2D area”; p. 23), but nonetheless concluded
70 that exudativores were not particularly distinctive in their metrics, since the only variable in

71 which they do not fall within the range of frugivore-insectivores is size (De Vries et al., 2023).
72 Whether the same situation holds in strepsirrhines has never been studied.

73 *Karanisia clarki*, an early strepsirrhine known from the earliest late Eocene (~37 million
74 years ago; Seiffert et al. 2005) of Egypt may have potentially consumed gums (López-Torres et
75 al. 2020; Seiffert 2012; Seiffert et al. 2003). The relationship of *K. clarki* to other strepsirrhines
76 has been a source of debate, with evidence suggesting that the taxon is a lorisid (Seiffert et al.
77 2003), a stem strepsirrhine (Seiffert et al. 2018), a crown strepsirrhine (Seiffert 2007), a stem
78 lorisoid (Seiffert 2007), or even a stem lemuroid (Seiffert et al. 2018). This uncertainty may be
79 due in part to both the plesiomorphic nature of *Karanisia* and the incompleteness of the material.
80 Additionally, it is possible that these phylogenetic analyses (Seiffert et al., 2003, 2018; Seiffert,
81 2007) lack either characters or operational taxonomic units that would be key to parse out
82 lorisoid relationships at a finer level. However, not in dispute is its identification as a
83 strepsirrhine, in light of the presence of a lower canine whose morphology indicates it was part
84 of a toothcomb. Previous analyses of the dental remains of *K. clarki* suggest that the taxon may
85 have been a mixed feeder, potentially feeding on fruit and leaves, based on measurement of
86 lower second molar shearing quotients (Marivaux et al. 2013). Previous DTA of *K. clarki*
87 suggests that the animal was a likely frugivore (Fulwood et al. 2021), whereas measurement of
88 enamel distribution of the canine (as part of the toothcomb) suggests that *K. clarki* may have
89 extracted and consumed gums as a ‘scraper’ (López-Torres et al. 2020). Scrapers are taxa that do
90 not actively gouge into tree to extract gums, but instead use their anterior teeth to remove plugs
91 of hardened saps to encourage the flow of new gums, which is a mode of extractive foraging
92 exhibited by some modern bushbabies (Burrows et al., 2015, 2020).

93 Here, we examine a large sample of lorisoid taxa that consume varying levels of gums
94 using DTA. We evaluate evidence for an association between molar form and exudativory as
95 another signal for exudate feeding. Several authors have suggested that exudates were an
96 important component in the diet of extinct strepsirrhines and the origin of Primates (Bearder and
97 Martin 1980; López-Torres et al. 2020; Martin 1979); therefore, methods for examining
98 adaptations to this unique mode of feeding may shed further light on the evolution and diet of
99 early primate taxa. Given the disagreement in the dietary categorization of *K. clarki*, and the fact
100 that it may have consumed some exudates, we also include a specimen of *K. clarki* in our
101 analysis of dental topography to assess the diet of this animal.

102 **Methods**

103 *The Sample*

104 The sample includes micro-CT scans of 52 specimens representing 17 extant species of
105 both Galagidae and Lorisidae and one extinct lorisoid species (Table 1, Figure 1). We analyzed a
106 single lower second molar (M₂) from each specimen and only included specimens that were
107 either unworn or lightly worn (with no dentine exposed in the occlusal basin) to reduce variation
108 introduced by wear. We included a single M₂ of *K. clarki* (dpc:21249). We downloaded all
109 included specimens as TIFF stacks from MorphoSource (Boyer et al. 2016), which represent
110 either scans of the original specimens or casts of the original specimens (Table S1).

111 *Dietary Categorization*

112 We assigned each extant taxon included in the analysis to two of a total of six dietary
113 categories based on previously collected behavioral data (Table 1). We broke up the dietary

114 categories into two groups, the first being the ‘mechanical’ dietary categories and the second
115 being the ‘exudate’ dietary categories. The ‘mechanical’ categories are those more traditionally
116 used in analyses of dental topography (e.g., Boyer 2008; Bunn et al. 2011; Fulwood et al. 2021;
117 Selig et al. 2019b; Winchester et al. 2014) and include frugivores, omnivores, and insectivores.
118 We assigned each taxon to one of these categories based on the major component of the diet that
119 requires mastication (i.e., excluding gums, as gums require little to no mastication [Nash, 1986])
120 regardless of the quantity of exudates they consume. Where the amount of fruit and insects they
121 consume is roughly equal, we considered the taxa to be omnivorous. Our study categorizes some
122 taxa differently than those of previous dental topographic analyses of lorises and bushbabies. For
123 example, others have categorized *Euoticus* and *Nycticebus* as frugivores, because of the large
124 quantity of gums consumed by these taxa, which they consider to fall under the umbrella of
125 frugivory (Fulwood et al., 2021). However, the non-gum component of the diet consumed by
126 *Euoticus* and *Nycticebus* is largely insects (e.g., Cabana et al. 2017; Nash 1986; Nash and
127 Burrows 2010; Streicher 2009); therefore, it is more appropriate to consider these taxa as
128 insectivorous when gum feeding is being considered independently, as we have done here.

129 The proportion of the diet made up by exudates makes the basis for defining the
130 ‘exudate’ dietary categories (Burrows and Nash, 2010; Burrows et al., 2015; 2020). We
131 considered intensive or obligate exudate feeders those taxa in which exudates make up more than
132 50% of the diet year-round, moderate exudate feeders those taxa in which exudates make up 50%
133 or less of the diet and/or consumed only seasonally, and non-exudate feeders those taxa that
134 consume no exudates (and so placed in the category ‘none’).

135 *Dental Topographic Analysis*

136 We measured three dental topographic metrics in our analysis. Dirichlet normal energy
137 (DNE) is a measure of surface curvature and therefore provides an idea as to how sharp a tooth
138 is, much like the shearing quotient (Bunn et al. 2011). Essentially, DNE provides a numerical
139 value for the deviation of a surface from being planar, and more highly curved or sharp surfaces
140 have higher DNE values. Three-dimensional orientation patch count rotated (3D-OPCR) is a
141 measurement of surface complexity, calculated as the number of discrete patches present on a
142 surface (Evans et al. 2007; Winchester 2016). The metric virtually partitions a tooth into patches
143 based on changes in topographic orientation relative to the eight compass directions. So, teeth
144 with more cusps and crests have more patches and therefore higher 3D-OPCR values. Finally,
145 the relief index (RFI) is a measure of relative crown height that contrasts the tooth's two-
146 dimensional planimetric footprint divided by its three-dimensional area (Boyer 2008; M'Kirera
147 and Ungar 2003; Ungar and M'Kirera 2003). Taller-crowned or more highly crested teeth have
148 higher RFI values. All three of these metrics covary with diet, particularly among euarchontan
149 taxa (Boyer 2008; Bunn et al. 2011; Fulwood et al. 2021; Selig et al. 2019b; Winchester et al.
150 2014). For example, insectivorous taxa tend to have sharper, more complex, taller, and more
151 highly crested molars than frugivores, therefore the insectivores tend to have higher DNE, 3D-
152 OPCR, and RFI values. Omnivorous taxa tend to have topographic values intermediate to the
153 insectivores and frugivores. Because of the close relationship between these metrics and diet,
154 DNE, 3D-OPCR, and RFI have previously been used in the reconstruction of diet or dietary
155 breadth in several fossil taxa (e.g., Berthaume et al. 2018; Boyer et al. 2010; de Vries et al. 2021;
156 Fulwood et al. 2021; Godfrey et al. 2012; Harper et al. 2019; Li et al. 2020; López-Torres et al.
157 2018; Morse et al., 2023; Prufrock, Boyer, et al. 2016; Prufrock, López-Torres, et al. 2016; Selig
158 et al. 2020, 2021a, 2021b; Selig and Silcox 2022; Thiery et al. 2017).

159 *Mesh Preparation and Measurement*

160 We used the following conventional methods for preparing the meshes for topographic
161 analyses. We imported the micro-CT scans into Avizo 8.1 (Visualization Sciences Group 2009)
162 where we segmented a M₂ from each specimen. Once segmented, we cropped M₂ surfaces along
163 the cervix to isolate the crowns (Boyer 2008; Bunn et al. 2011; Prufrock, López-Torres, et al.
164 2016), simplified each surface to 10,000 faces, and smoothed them to 100 iterations with the
165 lambda set at 0.6 to reduce noise (Bunn et al. 2011; Prufrock, López-Torres, et al. 2016). We
166 used MorphoTester 1.1.2 (Winchester 2016) to measure DNE, 3D-OPCR, and RFI. For DNE, we
167 used the default settings, with outlier removal set to 99.9% and implicit faring off, following
168 Bunn et al. (2011). For 3D-OPCR, we set the minimum patch size to five faces following
169 Winchester (2016). We recalculated the relief index as the natural log of the square root of the
170 tooth's two-dimensional planimetric footprint divided by its three-dimensional area following
171 Boyer (2008).

172 *Ancestral State Reconstruction*

173 We assembled the species used in the study based on a previously published tree (Pozzi
174 et al., 2015). We used this tree as the basis for an analysis of ancestral states for dental
175 topographic metrics in Mesquite 3.81 (Maddison and Maddison 2017) under parsimony (i.e.,
176 using the Analysis:Tree > Trace All Characters > Parsimony > Ancestral States option). We
177 performed the analysis using values for DNE, 3D-OPCR, and RFI. We used *Karanisia clarki* as
178 an outgroup, given its basal position (Seiffert 2007, Seiffert et al. 2018).

179 *Statistical Analysis*

180 For the statistical analyses, we used PAST 4.02 (Hammer et al. 2001). Because our data
181 were not normally distributed, we used non-parametric tests. We used the Mann-Whitney U to
182 test for differences in dental topography between the lorises and galagos, and Bonferroni
183 corrected pairwise Mann-Whitney U tests to evaluate differences between taxa based on their
184 ‘mechanical’, ‘exudate’, and combined mechanical/exudate categories. To test for an interaction
185 between their ‘mechanical’ category and their ‘exudate’ category, we used the non-parametric
186 two-way permutational multivariate analysis of variance (PERMANOVA). Finally, to visualize
187 variation in our sample, we used principal component analysis (PCA) using the correlation
188 matrix of species means. Because of the nature of our sample, we could not perform analyses
189 such as canonical variate analysis, which requires samples with more individuals within each
190 group than total number of groups.

191 **Results**

192 Mann-Whitney U tests indicate that the galagids have significantly higher DNE ($U = 214$,
193 $P = 0.039$), but not 3D-OPCR ($U = 314.5$, $P = 0.865$) or RFI ($U = 243$, $P = 0.129$) compared to
194 lorises (Figure 2). *Karanisia clarki* lies within the range of variation of both groups, with values
195 that are higher than the lorisid mean for DNE and RFI, making it more similar in those metrics to
196 galagids (Table 2).

197 When we grouped extant specimens by the ‘mechanical’ dietary category (Figure 3), the
198 Bonferroni corrected pairwise Mann-Whitney U tests indicate that the insectivores and
199 frugivores differ significantly from one another in values of DNE ($U = 84$, $P = 0.007$), but the
200 omnivores do not differ significantly from the insectivores ($U = 25$, $P = 0.118$) or the frugivores
201 ($U = 15$, $P = 0.908$). For the measurement of 3D-OPCR, there are no significant differences

202 between the insectivores or frugivores ($U = 170.5$, $P = 1$), the insectivores or omnivores ($U =$
203 48.5 , $P = 0.992$), or the omnivores or frugivores ($U = 23$, $P = 1$). Like in the case of DNE, for
204 RFI the insectivores and frugivores differ significantly from one another ($U = 57.5$, $P = <0.001$),
205 but the omnivores do not differ significantly from the insectivores ($U = 42$, $P = 0.609$) or the
206 frugivores ($U = 10$, $P = 0.305$). *Karanisia clarki* has relatively high curvature and particularly
207 relief, falling outside the interquartile range of frugivores and omnivores for DNE, and outside
208 the full range for those categories for RFI. As such, its values are more in keeping with those
209 calculated for the insectivorous taxa.

210 When we grouped extant specimens by ‘exudate’ dietary category (Figure 4), the
211 Bonferroni corrected pairwise Mann-Whitney U tests indicate that the non-exudate feeders have
212 significantly higher DNE compared to the intensive exudate feeders ($U = 72$, $P = 0.007$), but the
213 moderate exudate feeders do not differ from either the intensive ($U = 132$, $P = 1$) or the non-
214 exudate feeders ($U = 62$, $P = 0.206$). For the measurement of 3D-OPCR, there are no significant
215 differences between the intensive or moderate taxa ($U = 124.5$, $P = 1$), the intensive or non-
216 exudate feeders ($U = 144.5$, $P = 1$), or the moderate and non-exudate feeders ($U = 100$, $P = 1$).
217 Finally, the non-exudate feeders differ significantly from both the intensive ($U = 80.5$, $P = 0.015$)
218 and the moderate exudate feeders ($U = 35$, $P = 0.008$) in having higher RFI values, whereas the
219 intensive and moderate exudate feeders do not differ significantly ($U = 105.5$, $P = 0.620$).
220 *Karanisia clarki* has relatively high curvature and particularly relief, therefore, it more closely
221 resembles the non-exudate feeders in terms of its dental topography.

222 Results of the two-way PERMANOVA are significant (Table 3) and suggest that there is
223 an interaction between the ‘mechanical’ and ‘exudate’ dietary categories. To explore this

224 interaction in greater detail, we grouped specimens by a combination of their ‘mechanical’ and
225 ‘exudate’ feeding categories (Figure 5). According to the Bonferroni corrected pairwise Mann-
226 Whitney U tests, for both DNE and RFI, the Insectivore/ None category differs significantly
227 from the Insectivore/ Intensive category and the Frugivore/ Moderate category (Table 4). The
228 Insectivore/ Intensive category also differs significantly from the Insectivore/ Moderate category
229 as per the measurement of DNE. All other differences are non-significant.

230 The ancestral state reconstruction analysis reconstructs three key nodes (Figure 1) in
231 terms of their dental topography (Table 5). We reconstructed the ancestor of Galagidae as having
232 higher DNE, 3D-OPCR (only by 0.01 patches), and RFI values compared to Lorisidae. We
233 reconstructed the ancestor of Lorisidae as having topographic values intermediate to the
234 galagids and lorises, but that more closely resemble the galagids (see below).

235 Finally, the PCA shows the distribution of taxa in topographic morphospace (Figure 6).
236 Principal components 1 and 2 explain a cumulative 94.35% of the total variance and are
237 therefore the most informative (Table 6). Taxa in more positive morphospace have higher
238 topographic values compared to the taxa in more negative morphospace along PC 1, whereas
239 taxa that plot in more positive morphospace have relatively higher molar complexity compared
240 to those in more negative morphospace, characterized by greater molar relief along PC 2.
241 Principal component 1 therefore seems to separate the more insectivorous taxa in positive
242 morphospace from the more frugivorous taxa in negative morphospace. However, the
243 Insectivorous/ Intensive category plots in more negative morphospace along PC1, which is
244 consistent with their lower topographic values as discussed above.

245 All taxa categorized as insectivorous, with the exception of *N. bengalensis*, *N. coucang*,
246 and *Xanthonycticebus pygmaeus*, plot in positive morphospace, whereas the frugivorous and
247 omnivorous taxa plot in negative morphospace along PC1. Two species of *Otolemur* plot in close
248 proximity to one another, regardless of the fact that their diets seem to differ quite substantially.
249 There does not seem to be any clear pattern separating the lorises from the galagids as there
250 seems to be a complete overlap in the morphospace occupied by these groups. We also plotted
251 the three reconstructed nodes in the PCA, and as discussed above, our results suggest that the
252 lorisid ancestor was adapted to higher levels of frugivory compared to the galagid ancestor, with
253 the latter plotting in more positive morphospace along PC1. However, the lorisid ancestor
254 overlaps the morphospace of the “Insectivorous/ Intensive” taxa, which suggests that, rather than
255 necessarily being a frugivore, it may have been an insectivorous taxon with intensive exudate
256 feeding habits. In contrast, the galagid ancestor plots between the morphospace of the
257 “Insectivorous/ None” category and the “Insectivorous/ Intensive” category, leading to some
258 ambiguity in its interpretation. The lorisoid ancestor plots intermediate to the lorisid and galagid
259 ancestors, but plots in positive morphospace along PC1, slightly overlapping the “Insectivorous/
260 Intensive” taxa. *Karanisia clarki* plots in close proximity to the galagid and lorisoid ancestors.
261 Although it does not overlap the morphospace of any included groups, it plots close to the
262 “Insectivorous/ Intensive” *Euoticus elegantulus*.

263 Discussion

264 The results of the current study suggest that gum feeding may have an effect on the
265 morphology, and specifically the topography, of the lower molars. Although we do not find clear
266 separation between the intensive, moderate, or non-exudate feeding taxa, we do find that the

267 insectivorous taxa that consume exudates are characterized by an overall reduction in molar
268 topography compared to those insectivores that consume no exudates. Previous study of
269 nectivorous and sanguinivorous bats has demonstrated that they too are characterized by reduced
270 dental topography compared to insectivorous and omnivorous bats (Freeman 1995; López-
271 Aguirre et al. 2022), results consistent with our own findings. In contrast, others found a
272 somewhat different pattern for exudativorous platyrrhines (de Vries et al., 2023). In particular,
273 their finding of moderately higher RFI values for platyrrhine exudativores contrasts with our
274 results which show generally lower RFI values for this dietary category among lorisoids (Fig. 4).

275 Although our results point to a general reduction in molar topography among
276 exudativores, we found that the exudativores have particularly low molar curvature (as measured
277 by DNE). It is difficult to say why exudativores exhibit this reduction in molar topography (as do
278 nectivorous and sanguinivorous bats), but selection seems to be favoring lower molar topography
279 in taxa that spend proportionally less time masticating their food. Although there may be reason
280 to predict that exudativores would be characterized by a reduction in the intensity of selection for
281 molar topography as they use their molars less frequently, our results do not support this
282 hypothesis. A reduction of selection should lead to an increase in variation in topography, but
283 exudate-feeding taxa lack consistently higher variation in topography compared to non-
284 exudativorous taxa (as measured by the CV). That means, all else being equal, if an animal is not
285 doing as much mastication, we would predict that molar topography would decrease. There is
286 also evidence of directional selection on other traits related to a lesser emphasis on mastication.
287 In particular, previous work has demonstrated that gummivores are also characterized by a
288 reduction in the molar size (Boyer et al., 2021), and specifically the third molar (Burrows et al.,

289 2020). Therefore, results of previous studies (Burrows et al., 2020; Boyer et al., 2021), as well as
290 our own, point to an overall reduction in molar morphology among exudativores.

291 At the species level, we find some interesting patterns related to differences in diet as
292 well. For example, among species of *Nycticebus*, we see a gradient along PC1 with *N. javanicus*
293 in more positive morphospace, *N. coucang* in more negative morphospace, and *N. bengalensis* in
294 the most highly negative morphospace (Figure 6). Based on the available literature (Table 1), this
295 pattern appears to mirror differences in levels of exudate consumption among these taxa, with *N.*
296 *javanicus* spending the least of its time foraging on exudates (53.28%), *N. coucang* intermediate
297 (75%), and *N. bengalensis* spending the largest portion of its time foraging for exudates (92.9%).
298 Therefore, not only do we see large-scale patterns of morphology reflecting patterns of gum
299 feeding, but these topographic metrics may also pick up fine-scale signals within certain clades.
300 Conversely, however, both species of *Otolemur* plot near one another, yet only *O.*
301 *crassicaudatus* is known to consume gums. Likewise, the moderate exudativores plot in
302 distinctive morphospace, with the exception of the pottos, that plot near one another. It is
303 currently unclear what role phylogeny may play in explaining some of our results but this is an
304 avenue for further exploration (Winchester et al., 2014).

305 Others have provided three potential scenarios to explain the evolution of exudativory
306 within the lorisoids (Burrows et al., 2015, fig. 3). First, they suggest that the last common
307 ancestor (LCA) of the lorisoids, as well as of the lorises and galagids, were exudate feeders,
308 with exudativory having been lost in some lineages such as in the slender lorises (Burrows et al.,
309 2015). Second, they suggest that LCA of lorisoids was an exudate feeder, that the dietary regime
310 was lost in the LCA of lorises and galagids and reappeared in lineages such as the slow lorises

311 and greater galagos. And finally, they suggest that exudativory may not have been present in the
312 LCA of the lorisoids, lorisids, or galagids, but evolved as a novel feeding behaviour in taxa such
313 as the slow lorises and greater galagos (Burrows et al., 2015). Our ancestral state reconstruction
314 suggests that the LCA of lorisids share morphological similarities with modern intensive exudate
315 feeding insectivores. The galagid LCA plots between the insectivores that consume high levels
316 of exudates and those that consume none (Fig. 6), leading to a more ambiguous interpretation of
317 its diet. Although our results cannot definitively disprove one of these possible scenarios, our
318 current results suggest that the lorisid LCA may have been the more likely exudativore, while
319 levels of exudativory among the ancestral galagid is unclear. Our results also suggest that the
320 LCA of all lorisoids may have been most similar in their dietary adaptation to the intensive
321 exudate feeding insectivores; however, it plots very near the convex hull of the non-exudate
322 feeding insectivores as well, meaning a possible exudate component to its diet is not as likely as
323 in the case of the lorisid LCA. This is a fourth possible scenario where the lorisoid LCA is an
324 exudate feeder, exudativory is lost in the galagid LCA but retained in the lorisid lineage, and the
325 feeding regime is secondarily lost among some lorisids such as the slender lorises, and is
326 reacquired among some bushbabies such as *Euoticus* and *Otolemur crassicaudatus*.

327 Several authors have previously studied the dietary adaptations of *Karanisia* in some
328 detail (Fulwood et al. 2021; López-Torres et al. 2020; Marivaux et al. 2013) and their work
329 suggested that the animal may have been an omnivore or frugivore, and potentially an
330 exudativore. Our results suggest that *K. clarki* may have been an insectivore, and perhaps did not
331 rely very heavily on exudates. Differences here from previous analyses of dental topography
332 (Fulwood et al. 2021) may lie in the fact that our comparative sample is more limited within
333 Strepsirrhini, whereas others examined a more diverse sample of strepsirrhines, including lemurs

334 and other extinct taxa that evolved and diversified after *Karanisia* (Fulwood et al., 2021). Our
335 approach may allow for a refinement of conclusions given the suggested connection between
336 *Karanisia* and lorisoids. While our results provide new insight into the diet of *K. clarki*, which
337 was likely insectivorous, its consumption of exudates is unclear as the taxon plots in
338 morphospace between exudate feeders and non-exudate feeders. An independent proxy of
339 exudativory (i.e., incisor enamel thickness) suggests that this animal seemed to at least
340 occasionally use their anterior dentition to scrape for gums. Perhaps gums were a part of the diet
341 of *K. clarki*, but not as much as in some of the included scrapers such as *Euoticus*. An alternative
342 interpretation is that perhaps *K. clarki* was not scraping at gums but rather was using its anterior
343 teeth to pry at bark to extract insects, which we suggest may have been a major component of the
344 diet. Clearly, the question of the diet in *K. clarki* merits further research, potentially looking at
345 other, independent proxies for diet.

346 Overall, our results suggest that dental topography may provide some signal for exudate
347 feeding, particularly among insectivorous lorisoids. Although not a clear signal, DTA may be
348 useful for discerning this dietary habit among other extinct taxa. Used in tandem with methods
349 such as microwear analysis, which provide some insight into gum feeding (Marivaux et al.
350 2013), DTA could potentially help elucidate the larger, macroevolutionary implications and
351 consequences on the evolution of early primates.

352 **Data Availability Statement**

353 All data are available on MorphoSource.org, in the supplemental material, or upon
354 request from the corresponding author.

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- 520

521 **Figure Captions**

522 Figure 1. Relationship of extant strepsirrhines. Lower second molar meshes of *Karanisia clarki*
523 (dpc:21249), *Galago senegalensis* (AMNH:Mammals:M-187359), *Otolemur crassicaudatus*
524 (AMNH:Mammals:M-88062), *Sciurocheirus alleni* (MCZ:Mamm:64170 [reversed]),
525 *Perodicticus edwardsi* (AMNH:Mammals:M-269860), *Arctocebus calabarensis*
526 (AMNH:Mammals:M-207949), and *Nycticebus coucang* (USNM:MAMM:USNM 115496
527 [reversed]).

528 Figure 2. Boxplots of Dirichlet normal energy (DNE), three-dimensional orientation patch count
529 rotated (3D-OPCR), and relief index (RFI) of all extant taxa (*Perodicticus edwardsi*,
530 *Perodicticus potto*, *Arctocebus aureus*, *Arctocebus calabarensis*, *Euoticus elegantulus*, *Loris*
531 *lydekkerianus*, *Loris tardigradus*, *Nycticebus bengalensis*, *Nycticebus coucang*, *Nycticebus*
532 *javanicus*, *Xanthonycticebus pygmaeus*, *Otolemur crassicaudatus*, *Otolemur garnettii*,
533 *Sciurocheirus alleni*, *Galago moholi*, *Galago senegalensis*, *Galagoides demidoff*) at the family
534 level. The horizontal lines denote the median, the boxes represent the upper and lower quartiles,
535 and whiskers denote the highest and lowest values for each group. Bracket denotes significant
536 differences.

537 Figure 3. Boxplots of Dirichlet normal energy (DNE), three-dimensional orientation patch count
538 rotated (3D-OPCR), and relief index (RFI) of all extant taxa (*Perodicticus edwardsi*,
539 *Perodicticus potto*, *Arctocebus aureus*, *Arctocebus calabarensis*, *Euoticus elegantulus*, *Loris*
540 *lydekkerianus*, *Loris tardigradus*, *Nycticebus bengalensis*, *Nycticebus coucang*, *Nycticebus*
541 *javanicus*, *Xanthonycticebus pygmaeus*, *Otolemur crassicaudatus*, *Otolemur garnettii*,
542 *Sciurocheirus alleni*, *Galago moholi*, *Galago senegalensis*, *Galagoides demidoff*) at the

543 mechanical dietary category level. The horizontal lines denote the median, the boxes represent
544 the upper and lower quartiles, and whiskers denote the highest and lowest values for each group.
545 Brackets denote significant differences.

546 Figure 4. Boxplots of Dirichlet normal energy (DNE), three-dimensional orientation patch count
547 rotated (3D-OPCR), and relief index (RFI) of all extant taxa (*Perodicticus edwardsi*,
548 *Perodicticus potto*, *Arctocebus aureus*, *Arctocebus calabarensis*, *Euoticus elegantulus*, *Loris*
549 *lydekkerianus*, *Loris tardigradus*, *Nycticebus bengalensis*, *Nycticebus coucang*, *Nycticebus*
550 *javanicus*, *Xanthonycticebus pygmaeus*, *Otolemur crassicaudatus*, *Otolemur garnettii*,
551 *Sciurocheirus alleni*, *Galago moholi*, *Galago senegalensis*, *Galagoides demidoff*) at the exudate
552 category level. The horizontal lines denote the median, the boxes represent the upper and lower
553 quartiles, and whiskers denote the highest and lowest values for each group. Brackets denote
554 significant differences.

555 Figure 5. Boxplots of Dirichlet normal energy (DNE), three-dimensional orientation patch count
556 rotated (3D-OPCR), and relief index (RFI) of the extant taxa (*Perodicticus edwardsi*,
557 *Perodicticus potto*, *Arctocebus aureus*, *Arctocebus calabarensis*, *Euoticus elegantulus*, *Loris*
558 *lydekkerianus*, *Loris tardigradus*, *Nycticebus bengalensis*, *Nycticebus coucang*, *Nycticebus*
559 *javanicus*, *Xanthonycticebus pygmaeus*, *Otolemur crassicaudatus*, *Otolemur garnettii*,
560 *Sciurocheirus alleni*, *Galago moholi*, *Galago senegalensis*, *Galagoides demidoff*) at the
561 combined mechanical and exudate category level. The horizontal lines denote the median, the
562 boxes represent the upper and lower quartiles, and whiskers denote the highest and lowest values
563 for each group. Brackets denote significant differences.

RH: Lorisoid Dental Topography

564 Figure 6. Plot of the first two principal components. Biplot of loadings in top left corner. Values
565 in brackets indicate percent variance explained by each PC. Reconstructed values calculated
566 using ancestral state reconstruction. *Perodicticus edwardsi* (Pe), *Perodicticus potto* (Pp),
567 *Arctocebus aureus* (Aa), *Arctocebus calabarensis* (Ac), *Euoticus elegantulus* (Ee), *Loris*
568 *lydekkerianus* (Ll), *Loris tardigradus* (Lt), *Nycticebus bengalensis* (Nb), *Nycticebus coucang*
569 *(Nc)*, *Nycticebus javanicus* (Nj), *Xanthycticebus pygmaeus* (Xp), *Otolemur crassicaudatus*
570 *(Oc)*, *Otolemur garnettii* (Og), *Sciurocheirus alleni* (Sa), *Galago moholi* (Gm), *Galago*
571 *senegalensis* (Gs), *Galagoides demidovii* (Gd).

Table 1. Taxa included in the analysis, with dietary categories used, as well as proportions of feeding time spent for taxa where available.

Family	Species	N	Mechanical	Exudates	Proportions of feeding time	References
Lorisidae	<i>Perodicticus edwardsi</i>	4	Frugivore	Moderate	11% insects, 67% fruit, 22% exudates	(Nekaris and Bearder, 2007)
	<i>Perodicticus potto</i>	3	Frugivore	Moderate		(Burrows et al., 2020)
	<i>Arctocebus aureus</i>	1	Insectivore	None	87% insects, 17% fruit	(Nekaris and Bearder, 2007; Burrows et al., 2020)
	<i>Arctocebus calabarensis</i>	4	Insectivore	None		(Burrows et al., 2020)
	<i>Euoticus elegantulus</i>	5	Insectivore	Intensive	5% fruit, 75% exudates, 20% insects	(Nash, 1986)
	<i>Loris lydekkerianus</i>	2	Insectivore	None	96% insects	(Nekaris and Bearder, 2007; Burrows et al., 2015)
	<i>Loris tardigradus</i>	1	Insectivore	None	100% insects	(Nekaris and Bearder, 2007)
	<i>Nycticebus bengalensis</i>	3	Insectivore	Intensive	92.9% exudates, 0.3% fruit, 1.9% bark, 2.9% invertebrates	(Swapna et al., 2010; Nekaris, 2014)
	<i>Nycticebus coucang</i>	5	Insectivore	Intensive	75% exudates, 22.5-71% fruit, 2.5-29% insects*	(Nekaris and Bearder, 2007, Streicher et al., 2013)
	<i>Nycticebus javanicus</i>	2	Insectivore	Intensive	53.28% exudates, 15.82% fruit, 19.85% insects, 8.17% flowers, 1.93% leaves	(Nekaris, 2014; Cabana et al., 2017)
	<i>Xanthyonycticebus pygmaeus</i>	2	Insectivore	Intensive	60% exudates, 40% insects	(Streicher, 2009; Nekaris, 2014)
Galagidae	<i>Otolemur crassicaudatus</i>	5	Frugivore	Intensive	33% fruit, 62% exudates, 5% insects	(Bearder, 1987; Harcourt, 1986)
	<i>Otolemur garnettii</i>	1	Omnivore	None	50% fruit, 50% insects	(Nash, 1986; Bearder, 1987)
	<i>Sciurocheirus alleni</i>	3	Omnivore	None	50% fruit, 50% insects	(Burrows and Nash, 2010)
	<i>Galago moholi</i>	2	Insectivore	Moderate	48% exudates, 52% insects	(Bearder, 1987)

Table 1. Taxa included in the analysis, with dietary categories used, as well as proportions of feeding time spent for taxa where available.

	<i>Galago senegalensis</i>	4	Insectivore	Moderate	48% exudates, 52% insects	(Harcourt, 1986)
	<i>Galagoides demidoff</i>	4	Insectivore	None	19% fruit, 10% exudates, 70% insects	(Bearder, 1987)
Fossil	<i>Karanisia clarki</i> *	1	?	?		
	Total	52				

*Fruit has historically been argued to be a large part of the diet of *N. coucang*, however, more recent work has demonstrated that *N. coucang* prefers insects over fruit (Streicher et al., 2013). Therefore, we classify its diet secondarily as insectivorous.

Table 2. Summary statistics including mean, standard deviation (SD), and coefficient of variation (CV) for the measurement of Dirichlet normal energy (DNE), three-dimensional orientation patch count rotated (3D-OPCR), and relief index (RFI).

Taxon	N	DNE			3D-OPCR			RFI		
		Mean	SD	CV	Mean	SD	CV	Mean	SD	CV
<i>Karanisia clarki</i>	1	234.70	-	-	55.50	-	-	0.5315	-	-
<i>Galago senegalensis</i>	4	260.57	17.49	6.71	58.19	5.89	10.11	0.498	0.043	8.688
<i>Galago moholi</i>	2	307.46	57.27	18.63	70.88	11.50	16.21	0.488	0.009	1.936
<i>Galagoides demidoff</i>	4	285.77	23.43	8.20	56.94	3.50	6.14	0.545	0.019	3.403
<i>Otolemur crassicaudatus</i>	5	211.66	48.80	23.05	56.85	9.24	16.26	0.456	0.045	9.916
<i>Otolemur garnettii</i>	1	197.20	-	-	59.25	-	-	0.459	-	-
<i>Sciurocheirus alleni</i>	3	209.79	21.38	10.19	53.33	3.817	7.16	0.485	0.006	1.233
<i>Euoticus elegantulus</i>	5	244.16	7.72	3.16	55.98	2.54	4.54	0.518	0.028	5.425
<i>Perodicticus edwardsi</i>	4	168.51	29.46	17.48	55.25	8.77	15.87	0.442	0.022	5.017
<i>Perodicticus potto</i>	3	185.42	51.82	27.95	54.92	7.84	14.28	0.454	0.012	2.673
<i>Arctocebus aureus</i>	1	245.04	-	-	80.13	-	-	0.457	-	-
<i>Arctocebus calabarensis</i>	4	306.67	55.35	18.05	60.53	6.48	10.71	0.555	0.052	9.445
<i>Loris lydekkerianus</i>	2	253.20	25.02	9.88	57.44	5.21	9.08	0.531	0	0
<i>Loris tardigradus</i>	1	324.28	-	-	56.5	-	-	0.499	-	-
<i>Xanthonycticebus pygmaeus</i>	2	237.70	31.93	13.43	64.31	5.215	8.11	0.473	0.001	0.174
<i>Nycticebus javanicus</i>	2	240.27	6.11	2.55	60.31	0.62	1.03	0.506	0.016	3.122
<i>Nycticebus bengalensis</i>	3	161.41	28.66	17.75	45.08	2.31	5.12	0.461	0.011	2.307
<i>Nycticebus coucang</i>	5	196.59	24.74	12.59	56.00	3.77	6.72	0.472	0.026	5.556

Table 3. Results of the non-parametric two-way permutational multivariate ANOVA (PERMANOVA).

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p
Mechanical Category	34308	2	17154	4.621	<0.001
Exudate category	28292	2	14146	3.811	<0.001
Interaction	-68528	4	-17132	-4.616	0.025
Residual	15590	42	3711.9		
Total	14997	50			

Table 4. Results of the Bonferroni corrected Mann-Whitney U comparing medians for each dietary categorization for each dental topographic metric. Bolded values indicate that the difference is statistically significant. Non-applicable values are represented with an X.

DNE	Frugivore/ Intensive	Insectivore / Intensive	Frugivore/ Moderate	Insectivore / Moderate	Omnivore/ None
Insectivore/ Intensive	1	X	X	X	X
Frugivore/ Moderate	1	0.632	X	X	X
Insectivore/ Moderate	1	0.035	0.080	X	X
Omnivore/ None	1	1	1	0.213	X
Insectivore/ None	0.352	0.001	0.009	1	0.066
3D-OPCR					
Insectivore/ Intensive	1	X	X	X	X
Frugivore/ Moderate	1	1	X	x	X
Insectivore/ Moderate	1	1	1	X	X
Omnivore/ None	1	1	1	1	x
Insectivore/ None	1	1	1	1	1
RFI					
Insectivore/ Intensive	1	X	X	X	X
Frugivore/ Moderate	1	0.064	X	X	X
Insectivore/ Moderate	1	1	0.276	X	X
Omnivore/ None	1	1	0.446	1	X
Insectivore/ None	0.066	0.031	0.017	0.659	0.269

Table 5. Results of the ancestral state reconstruction for each topographic metric.

Node	DNE	3D-OPCR	RFI
Lorisoidea	242.17	57.50	0.512
Galagidae	249.74	57.51	0.517
Lorisidae	238.33	58.49	0.496

Table 6. Summary of the results of the Principal Component Analysis (PCA).

PC	Eigenvalue	% Variance	DNE (Loadings)	3D-OPCR (Loadings)	RFI (Loadings)
1	1.76760	58.920	0.72037	0.34833	0.59978
2	1.06297	35.432	0.03719	0.84410	-0.53489
3	0.16943	5.648	-0.69260	0.40762	0.59511